

Synthesis of Some 2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxy-, -4-amino- and- 4-phenylamino-quinoline Derivatives and of 2- (4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-ethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline Derivatives

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2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives have been synthesised by cyclising the crude condensation products obtained by condensing 4-methoxybenz-aryl imidochlorides with ethyl sodioacetate. Corresponding 4-amino and 4-phenylamino-quinoline derivatives have been prepared by treating these hydroxyquinoline derivatives with dry ammonia and dry aniline respectively in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. 2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-ethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives have been obtained by reducing the acetyl group in 3-position by Clemmensen's method.

2-Aryl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives were prepared by Just¹ by condensing imidochlorides with diethyl sodiomalonate and cyclising the mono-condensation products obtained. This method was successfully used by subsequent workers². Shah *et al.*³ used ethyl sodioacetate instead of diethyl sodiomalonate for condensation with imidochlorides and obtained 2-aryl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxyquinolines.

In the present investigation, 4-methoxybenz-aryl imidochlorides (Ia, Ib, Ic, and Id; see earlier paper⁴) were successfully condensed with ethyl sodioacetate and the crude condensation products were directly cyclised by heating them under reduced pressure to 2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc, and IId; $\text{Y}=\text{COMe}$).

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1. *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2623; 1886, 19, 983, 1467, 1545.

2. Feja and Funchs, *Vonatsk.*, 1931, 57, 62; Shah and Heermaneck, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 428; Elderfield *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1272; Kulkarni and Shah, *this Journal*, 1949, 20, 171.

3. *This Journal*, 1949, 26, 121; 1950, 27, 111.

4. *This issue*, p. 27.

These 4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives, on treating with dry ammonia gas in presence of phosphorus oxychloride, furnished the corresponding 4-aminoquinoline derivatives (IIIa, IIIb, IIIc, and IIId; R=H), the hydroxyl group having been replaced by amino group. This provided an easy method for the synthesis of 4-aminoquinoline derivatives. Similarly, 4-phenylaminoquinoline derivatives (IIIa, IIIb, and IIIc; R=Ph) were obtained by treating the corresponding 4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives with dry aniline in presence of phosphorus oxychloride.

The Clemmensen reduction of the hydroxyquinoline derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc, and IIId; Y=COMe) furnished the corresponding 2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3-ethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc, and IIId; Y=Et), the acetyl group in 3-position having been reduced to ethyl.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxyquinoline Derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc & IIId; Y=COMe): Condensation of 4-Methoxybenz-aryl Imidochlorides with Ethyl Sodiaoacetate.—4-Methoxybenz-aryl imidochloride⁴ (Ia, Ib, Ic or Id; see Table I for quantities used) was added to the suspension of ethyl sodiaoacetate (from 11 ml of ester and 1 g. of pulverised sodium) in dry toluene (100 ml) and the mixture was refluxed in an oil bath (kept at 120-30°) for about 4 hrs. It was poured into water and extracted with ether. The residue obtained after removal of the ether was distilled below 130° under reduced pressure to remove toluene and the unchanged ester.

The crude condensation products, thus obtained, were in a pasty form ~~and did not~~ solidify. These were then directly cyclised by heating in an oil bath at 200-10° under 10 mm pressure till the evolution of bubbles had ceased. The hard solid masses obtained on cooling were extracted with boiling aqueous 10% solution of NaOH. The clear alkaline extracts were neutralised by adding HCl (dil.) to the neutral point (excess of the acid should be avoided as quinoline may dissolve) when the products separated which were crystallised from appropriate solvents (Table I).

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazene derivatives were prepared by refluxing the ethanolic solutions of the hydroxyquinoline derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc, and IIId; Y=COMe) (0.1 g. in 5 ml) with ethanolic solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.2 g. in 2 ml) for 8 hours. The red crystalline substances separating on cooling were crystallised from ethanol (Table I).

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-aminoquinoline Derivatives (IIIa, IIIb, IIIc & IIId; R=H).—Dry ammonia gas was slowly bubbled into a mixture of 4-hydroxyquinoline derivative (IIa, IIb, IIc or IIId; Y=COMe) (2 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (15 ml) for about an hour till it was fully saturated. The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. Crushed ice was then added and the white solid (a phosphorus complex) separating was removed by filtration; the filtrate was neutralised by NaOH solution. The precipitated product was crystallised from appropriate solvents (Table II).

TABLE I

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxyquinolines (II) and their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones

M=4-methoxybenz. I=imidochloride P=2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl. Q=quinoline.

Imidochloride used.	Quinoline deriva- tive (II, Y=COMe).	Cryst. appear- ance.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.	M.P. of 2,4- D.N.P. and their for- mula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.
1. M-anilide-I (Ia) (10 g.)	P-4-hydroxy-Q (IIa)	*Long needles	236-37°	3.0 g.	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	C : 73.94% H : 5.26 N : 5.03	73.72% 5.12 4.77	235-27° C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₅	14.68 14.70
2. M-o-toluidide-I (Ib) (Imidochloride prepa- red from 10. g. of the amide)	P-4-hydroxy-8- methyl-Q (IIb)	*Rectangular plates	246-47°	0.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	C : 74.32 H : 5.45 N : 4.32	74.26 5.53 4.50	300-301° C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₆	14.19 14.37
3. M-p-anilide-I (Ic) (10 g.)	P-4-hydroxy-6- methoxy-Q (IIc)	†Fine needles	205-90°	1.5	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	C : 70.70 H : 5.42 N : 4.44	70.59 5.36 4.33	Above 300° C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₇ N ₅	13.60 13.91
4. M-p-phenesulfide-I (Id) (10 g.)	P-4-hydroxy- 6-ethoxy-Q. (IIc)	*Needles	271-72°	0.65	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N	C : 71.39 H : 5.78 N : 4.09	71.21 5.64 4.16	Above 300° C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₅	13.21 13.53

N.B. All hydroxyquinoline derivatives are very sparingly soluble in HCl (dil.)

† From acetic acid.

* From ethanol.

TABLE II

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-aminoquinoline derivatives (III; R=H).

P=2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl. Q=quinoline.

4-Aminoquinoline derivatives (III; R=H).	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1. P-4-amino-Q (IIIa)	*Fines needles	164.65°	1.0 g.	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	C : 73.75% H : 5.32 N : 9.51	73.97% 6.48 9.58
2. P-4-amino-8-methyl-Q (IIIb)	*Do	167.66°	1.0	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₂	C : 74.61 H : 5.69 N : 8.66	74.51 5.88 8.15
**3. P-4-amino-6-methoxy-Q (IIIc)	†Needles	193.64°	0.2	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂	C : 69.85 H : 5.59 N : 8.99	70.06 5.73 8.69
**4. P-4-amino-8-ethoxy-Q (IIId)	*Fines needles	197.68°	0.2	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₂	C : 71.15 H : 5.76 N : 8.99	71.43 5.95 8.33

N.B. All aminoquinoline derivatives are very soluble in dilute 1,1-dichloroacetic acid.

*From ethanol.

†From benzene.

*The crude products obtained from the reaction mixture show a range in m.p (175-236°) in case of IIIc and 160-76° in case of IIId). By repeated crystallization of IIIc from benzene and IIId from ethanol pure substances were obtained.

TABLE III

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-phenylaminoquinolines (III: R=Ph).

P=2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3 acetyl- Q=quinoline.

4-Phenylaminoquinoline derivative (III: R=Ph).	Solvent for crys- tallisation.	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Recd.
1. P-4-phenylamino-Q (IIIa)	Benzene	Needles	213-14°	1.2 g.	$C_{24}H_{20}O_2N_2$	C : 78.1% H : 5.25 N : 7.43	78.31% 5.43 7.60
2. P-4-phenylamino-6-methyl-Q (IIIb)	Ethanol	Do	143-44°	0.8	$C_{23}H_{19}O_2N_2$	C : 76.75 H : 5.81 N : 7.01	78.53 5.75 7.32
3. P-4-phenylamino-6-methoxy-Q (IIIc)	Do	Rhombic plates	163-64°	0.5	$C_{25}H_{21}O_3N_2$	C : 75.20 H : 5.37 N : 6.63	75.37 5.52 7.03

N. B. P-4-phenylamino-6-ethoxy-Q (IIIc) could not be isolated in a pure condition from the reaction of aniline on P-4-hydroxy-6-ethoxy-Q (IIId; Y=COEt) in presence of phosphorus oxychloride. A product was obtained which crystallised from ethanol but gave a range in m.p. (150-40°). Fractional crystallisation from ethanol and other solvents did not succeed.

TABLE IV

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-ethyl-4-hydroxyquinolines (II: Y=Et).

P'=2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3-ethyl-. Q=quinoline.

Quinoline derivative (II: Y=Et).	*Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1. P'-4-hydroxy-Q (IIa)	Needles	250-51°	0.4 g.	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ O ₂ N	C : 77.22 H : 5.85 N : 4.79	77.43% 6.09 5.01
2. P'-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-Q (IIb)	Thick plates	230-32°	0.4	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	C : 77.65 H : 6.31 N : 4.45	77.81 6.48 4.77
3. P'-4-hydroxy-6-methoxy-Q (IIc)	Needles	266-67°	0.3	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	C : 73.80 H : 6.28 N : 4.40	73.78 6.15 4.53
4. P'-4-hydroxy-6-ethoxy-Q (IId)	Do	280-81°	0.3	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ O ₃ N	C : 74.52 H : 6.67 N : 4.64	74.30 6.50 4.33

*Crystallised from ethanol.

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-phenylaminoquinoline Derivatives (IIIa, IIIb, IIIc & IIId; R=Ph).—Distilled aniline was added dropwise to the mixture of 4-hydroxyquinoline derivative (IIa, IIb, IIc or IId; Y=COMe) (2 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (15 ml); the mixture was heated for about 15 minutes on a boiling water bath (when it turned red) and then kept overnight at room temperature. It was poured over crushed ice ~~where~~ and the product separated in pasty form. On washing it several times with HCl (dil.) and then with water, a yellow solid was obtained. It was crystallised from an appropriate solvent (Table III).

2-(4'-Methoxy)phenyl-3-ethyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc & IId; Y=Et) were prepared by the Clemmensen reduction of the corresponding 2-(4'-methoxy)phenyl-3-acetyl-4-hydroxyquinoline derivatives (IIa, IIb, IIc, and IId; Y=COMe) (0.5 g.) with zinc amalgam (from 5 g. of zinc dust) and HCl (1:1; 50 ml) by refluxing for about 4 hours (HCl was added in small lots during the period).

The solutions were filtered from unchanged zinc when hot and then allowed to cool. The reduced products separated as white solids. These were washed with water and crystallised from appropriate solvents (Table IV).